

FLIGHT OVER FIGHT: RETHINKING THE JAPA PHENOMENON IN CONTEMPORARY NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The japa phenomenon which denotes Nigeria's contemporary wave of youth emigration has largely been examined through the lenses of economic aspiration, political disenchantment, and social mobility. This paper rethinks japa through the metaphor of the "fight-or-flight" response, framing it as a collective preference for flight over fight in the face of structural dysfunctions. Drawing on sociological and psychological insights, the paper explores how Nigerian youths interpret migration not merely as a search for opportunities but as an act of survival, self-preservation, and resistance through withdrawal. While "fight" would imply staying behind to engage with or transform the system, "flight" represents an exit strategy from chronic insecurity, unemployment, corruption, and deteriorating public services. Using qualitative data from the Lagos site of a larger multi-sited project, the paper interrogates the implications of this choice for Nigeria's development, nation-building, and civic engagement. It argues that the japa wave reflects both a crisis of trust in state institutions and a reconfiguration of agency, where mobility becomes a tool of negotiation rather than confrontation. Ultimately, the study situates japa within broader debates on youth, migration, and the politics of exit in Africa. The paper concludes by suggesting that addressing the japa phenomenon requires not only structural reforms in governance and service delivery but also renewed frameworks for civic trust and youth engagement.

Key words: Japa phenomenon, flight, fight, politics of exit, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

Nigeria's contemporary migration wave, popularly termed *japa*, is increasingly described by young people as an urgent escape from threatening conditions. One Lagos respondent captured this bluntly:

"Nigeria is no more safe in every area, and it makes us feel so insecure. Even the government cannot guarantee security for themselves, so we are doing this *japa* thing all of a sudden in order to secure a future for ourselves and families." This sentiment illustrates the everyday precarity that renders migration less a matter of choice than of necessity, thereby positioning *japa* within a logic of "flight over fight."

Migration itself is not a new phenomenon in human society. From prehistoric times, people have moved from one place to another, often leaving adverse conditions in search of more favourable environments. As Naranjo (1995) notes, "people have moved from place to place and have joined and separated again throughout our past, and we have incorporated it into our songs, stories, and myths because we must continually remember that, without movement, there is no life." (p. 250). In Nigeria, however, migration in recent years has been nicknamed *Japa*, a Yoruba term meaning "to run swiftly away from a threat." The term, which began as an informal expression, has evolved into a powerful metaphor for a generational response to economic hardship, political instability, and dwindling prospects at home. From students pursuing education overseas, to skilled professionals relocating for better work opportunities, to low-skilled migrants risking irregular routes, *japa* encapsulates both the urgency and scale of contemporary Nigerian migration. The phenomenon is not only reshaping demographics and labour markets but also redefining how young people negotiate their futures in the face of systemic dysfunction.

This paper rethinks *japa* through the metaphor of "flight over fight." Borrowed from psychology's classic "fight-or-flight" response, the framing highlights migration as a collective strategy of flight in the face of overwhelming threats. Instead of staying to "fight", that is, to resist or transform Nigeria's structural challenges, many youths choose to "fly," relocating to destinations perceived as safer, more stable, and more rewarding. This shift raises important sociological questions: What drives the preference for flight over fight? How does it reflect changing forms of agency and resistance? And what does it mean for Nigeria's development and governance?

By situating *japa* within the frameworks of Hirschman's Exit, Voice, and Loyalty, the fight-or-flight response, and the push-pull migration theory, this paper examines how migration becomes a rational and agentive response to systemic crises. It argues that the *Japa* phenomenon is not simply about individual aspiration but about collective survival, silent protest, and the politics of exit.

Conceptual/Literature Review

The term *japa*, a Yoruba coinage meaning "to flee swiftly," has entered both popular and scholarly discourse as shorthand for the widespread migration of Nigerian youths in search of better opportunities abroad (Nwobodo, 2024; Okunade & Awosusi, 2023). Initially emerging as urban slang, *japa* has evolved into a metaphor that goes beyond physical relocation. It encapsulates disillusionment with governance, systemic dysfunction, and a reorientation of youth aspirations toward transnational horizons (; Adegoke, 2023; Okunade & Awosusi, 2023).

Scholarly engagement with japa has primarily emphasized its socio-economic dimensions. Studies highlight its implications for labor markets and higher education, pointing to large-scale brain drain, professional exodus, and the attendant consequences for national development (Jibromah, 2024; Liu, 2023). Others situate japa within the broader crisis of governance, showing how corruption, insecurity, and weak institutions reinforce migration as a rational survival strategy (Eze, 2023; Olawale, 2021). Beyond structural pressures, migration has also been interpreted as a cultural project: a rite of passage, a family investment strategy, and a collective imaginary of hope (Ojo & Balogun, 2022; Omeje, 2023). These perspectives underscore how japa has become both a social aspiration and a coping mechanism.

More broadly, migration studies have drawn on classical frameworks such as the push-pull theory (Ravenstein, 1885, 1889; Lee, 1966), which conceptualizes migration as a response to negative “push” conditions (e.g., poverty, unemployment, insecurity) and positive “pull” attractions abroad (Anene et al, 2019; Saraswati et al., 2025; Urbanski, 2022). While these models capture the structural drivers of migration, they often reduce migration to an individual economic decision, underplaying the cultural meanings and psychological frames through which people interpret crisis and opportunity.

Recent scholarship on African youth migration has sought to move beyond structural determinism by foregrounding youth agency, spirituality, and aspiration (Awumbila et al., 2020; Carling & Collins, 2018;). This body of work emphasizes that migration is not merely a rational calculation but also a symbolic act of survival, hope, and resistance. Within the Nigerian context, however, there is still limited theorization of why flight, in the form of emigration, has emerged as the dominant response, while fight - expressed through civic engagement, protest, or reform - has lost traction among many young people.

To address this gap, this paper draws on Cannon’s (1932) fight-or-flight metaphor alongside Hirschman’s (1970) exit-voice-loyalty framework. Together, these lenses illuminate how Nigerian youths increasingly frame migration as a survivalist instinct and a political choice of “exit” over “voice.” Unlike existing studies that interpret japa mainly through brain drain or labor mobility, this approach repositions it as a psychological and sociological response to systemic crisis, highlighting the cultural logics that sustain “flight over fight.”

Theoretical Framework

This study adopts a hybrid theoretical lens, combining Hirschman’s (1970) Exit, Voice, and Loyalty model; Canon’s (1915/1932) fight-or-flight response metaphor, and the push-pull migration theory. Together, these frameworks illuminate the japa phenomenon as a complex response to structural crises in Nigeria.

Hirschman’s model explains how individuals and groups react to dissatisfaction with institutions. ‘Voice’ entails staying to demand change, ‘loyalty’ implies enduring despite hardships, while ‘exit’ represents withdrawal or departure. The japa phenomenon thus, aligns closely with “exit,” as Nigerian youths increasingly choose migration over engagement or endurance. Viewed from this perspective, japa is not mere escapism but a deliberate strategy of refusal, where leaving becomes a form of silent protest against a failing state.

The fight-or-flight metaphor (Canon, 1915; 1932) deepens this analysis by framing japa as a collective “flight” response to overwhelming threats. Just as organisms faced with danger instinctively choose survival over confrontation, Nigerian youths interpret insecurity,

unemployment, corruption, and poor governance as existential dangers. Japa therefore, emerges as a form of self-preservation in which flight takes precedence over fight.

Finally, push-pull migration theory (Ravenstein, 1885/1889; Lee, 1966) contextualizes these choices within broader migration studies. Nigeria's structural dysfunctions ranging from poverty, unemployment, leadership failure, and insecurity operate as powerful push factors, while opportunities for education, work, and safety abroad serve as pull factors. Together, these forces reinforce "flight" as a rational option.

Through these perspectives, the paper situates the japa phenomenon as both a structural outcome and an agentic choice. Migration here represents a negotiation between survival instincts, rational cost-benefit analysis, and systemic disillusionment, thereby reframing japa as the politics of flight over fight.

Methodological Note

This paper is primarily theoretical engaging critically with concepts from migration studies, youth studies, and the sociology of religion. The aim is to contribute to the study of migration in Africa, with a particular focus on the contemporary Japa phenomenon in Nigeria. However, to enrich the discussion, the paper draws selectively on existing qualitative materials generated from the Lagos field site of a larger multi-sited project titled "The Religious and Spiritual Lives of Transnational Young People of African Migrant Background". This project which started in 2023 and scheduled to end in 2026, is conducted across Nigeria, South Africa, Zimbabwe, and the United Kingdom, and seeks to understand how young people negotiate religion, spirituality, and mobility within transnational contexts. While the present paper does not undertake fresh empirical analysis, excerpts from this body of material are included to illustrate and ground theoretical arguments to avoid abstraction and instead highlight the lived realities that underlie the Japa phenomenon. Thus, the use of existing data here is illustrative rather than analytical, serving as a bridge between theoretical reflection and empirical experience.

Youth agency and the choice of flight

While structural dysfunctions create the conditions for Japa, the phenomenon cannot be understood solely as a reaction to external pressures. It also represents an expression of youth agency - the capacity of young Nigerians to make strategic choices in the face of precarity. Japa, in this sense, is not simply an escape but a deliberate act of reimagining one's future beyond the boundaries of a failing system (Carling & Collins, 2018).

Japa as survival and self-preservation

For many youths, remaining in Nigeria is increasingly seen as a risk to both livelihood and well-being. The inability of the state to guarantee security, provide employment, or ensure access to basic services pushes young people to treat migration as a survival strategy. One Lagos respondent captured this starkly:

"Staying here feels like gambling with your future. If you can find a way out, then be prepared to take whatever you see, because tomorrow is never certain in this country" (Interview, Lagos, 2024).

Scholars have also emphasized this survivalist framing of migration. Adepoju (2020) describes African youth migration as a pragmatic response to economic and political insecurity, rather than a purely adventurous pursuit. In this sense, Japa embodies the “flight” dimension of the fight-or-flight metaphor, where exit becomes an act of self-preservation.

Japa as Silent Resistance

Although outward migration may appear as withdrawal, it can also be interpreted as a form of resistance through exit. By leaving, youths withdraw their labour, skills, and loyalty from a state that has failed them. As one young professional remarked:

“It’s doesn’t mean we who want to japa, or those who have done so, don’t love Nigeria. Truth is: we’re just fed-up investing in a system that has turned against us. Leaving is my way of saying I can’t take it anymore” (FGD, Lagos, 2024).

This resonates with Hirschman’s (1970) classic formulation of exit as a political act: a silent yet powerful critique of state failure. Recent scholarship echoes this view, suggesting that youth migration from Africa increasingly functions as a vote of no confidence in governance systems (Dading, 2022).

Narratives of Hope and Aspiration

Beyond survival, Japa is framed as a pathway to hope, dignity, and aspiration. Social media narratives, success stories of diaspora communities, and visible improvements in the lives of migrant families reinforce the perception that japa is the most viable route to self-fulfilment. As one participant explained:

“My friends post videos and pictures of their new lives abroad. I see clean environments, respect for humanity, good jobs, and relaxed physical appearance. It makes me believe that my own dreams are possible too” (FGD, Lagos, 2024).

Scholars note that such narratives are not unique to Nigeria but part of broader migration imaginaries that shape youth aspirations across Africa (Mabogunje, 2021). These imaginaries highlight agency not as passive reaction but as active construction of a desirable future, even if it requires leaving one’s homeland.

Diaspora Activism and “Fighting from Afar”

Importantly, choosing flight does not necessarily preclude forms of “fight.” Many in the diaspora remain engaged in Nigerian political and social life, contributing through remittances, knowledge transfer, or transnational activism. As one UK-based respondent described:

“I may not always be physically in Nigeria, but I’m still fighting for change. Through my network here, we raise funds, speak up online, and support local movements back home” (Interview, Lagos, 2024).

This supports arguments that diasporas increasingly act as agents of change in their home countries, blending economic contributions with political activism (Awumbila, 2017; Mercer et al., 2008;). Online campaigns, advocacy for governance reforms, and diaspora-led philanthropic initiatives illustrate how youths may continue to “fight” indirectly, even after exiting. Thus, Japa represents a hybrid agency, where flight becomes the primary choice but does not foreclose other modes of engagement.

Implications of Flight over Fight

The choice of flight over fight among Nigerian youth carries far-reaching implications that extend beyond individual survival strategies, touching the nation's social fabric, political culture, and development trajectory. While migration offers immediate relief for individuals, it also produces ripple effects that shape communities, institutions, and the nation's future.

Brain drain and developmental gaps

One of the most visible consequences of japa is the massive outflow of skilled labour. Professionals in health, education, technology, and other critical sectors are leaving in unprecedented numbers. This large-scale migration intensifies Nigeria's human capital crisis. Health workers, educators, engineers who japa create widening service gaps that weaken national development prospects. The japa phenomenon thus accelerates a vicious cycle: as institutions deteriorate, more youths choose exit, further undermining the very systems that might have supported collective resilience. A respondent in Lagos captured this precarity as follows:

“Almost every doctor I know has left or is processing papers. It is like the hospitals are emptying out, and those of us left behind are struggling to cope” (Interview, Lagos, 2024).

This mirrors research showing how migration exacerbates skill shortages, with Africa losing vital human capital needed for development (Docquier & Rapoport, 2012). The departure of young professionals, while rational at the individual level, imposes collective costs on already fragile institutions.

Transnational Family disruptions and community dynamics

The japa wave is also transforming family and community life. While remittances and diaspora support provide new opportunities for those left behind, the emotional and social costs of separation reshape kinship structures. For some, migration offers collective uplift; for others, it produces fragmentation, dependence, and new vulnerabilities. A left-behind youth expressed this ambivalence:

“... my mother sends me foreign currency, but sometimes I wonder and ask myself why I am the person that has to live like this. When I visit my friend's houses, I find their moms around while I do not really have mine around to talk to. Sometime it makes me feel like an outcast” (Interview, Lagos, 2025)

Scholars warn that while remittances alleviate poverty, they may also create dependencies and emotional gaps within families (Mazzucato & Schans, 2011). Thus, the gains of migration are tempered by new vulnerabilities in social reproduction.

Political quietism and the erosion of voice

The preference for flight can weaken local struggles for reform. As one Lagos-based activist observed:

“because of government's high handedness during the EndSars protest, and the reckless manipulation of INEC and the courts, many of the brightest minds who could have fought for change have either gone or are fighting for visas” (FGD, Lagos, 2024).

This echoes Hirschman's (1970) warning that widespread “exit” may silence “voice,” leaving institutions unreformed. Nigeria risks losing not just its workforce but also the civic energy required to hold leaders accountable.

Diaspora Influence and Transnational Engagement

Flight, however, does not imply absolute withdrawal from the national project. Diaspora communities are increasingly influential actors in Nigerian politics and development. Online activism, advocacy for reforms, and philanthropic interventions illustrate how youths who “fly” may continue to “fight” from a distance. This suggests that flight and fight are not mutually exclusive, but rather interwoven across transnational spaces. A London-based respondent explained:

“We may not be on the streets protesting, but online we amplify the struggles of Nigerians back home. We can fight differently, even from outside” (Interview, Lagos, 2024).

Research confirms that diasporas often play ambivalent roles - both supporting home-country reforms and, at times, reinforcing dependency through remittances (Umeh et al 2024). This suggests that while flight diminishes direct civic participation, it can reconfigure activism into transnational forms.

Redefinition of citizenship, loyalty, and generational futures

Youth exit can also be read as a silent reconfiguration of citizenship. Choosing flight signals a withdrawal of loyalty from the state, reflecting Hirschman’s “exit” as a form of critique. This withdrawal raises questions about the future of civic participation: when the most vibrant demographic cohort disengages through migration, the possibilities of reform-through-voice diminish. Also, japa reshapes how young Nigerians imagine their belonging. For many, national identity becomes secondary to the pursuit of mobility and global citizenship. As one respondent put it:

“Nigeria is not a bad place, but it does not seem to hold any stakes for my future. My future is wherever I can live with dignity” (FGD, Lagos, 2024).

This generational reorientation challenges state legitimacy and raises questions about Nigeria’s capacity to inspire loyalty among its youth. As Adeyamju et al (2024) argues, when young people decouple their aspirations from the nation-state, governance crises become existential rather than cyclical.

Governance and the Politics of Exit

The growing politics of exit challenges state legitimacy. When flight becomes normalized as the rational option, it reflects a crisis of trust in governance. Unless structural reforms are undertaken, the state risks further alienation of its citizens, with migration functioning as a barometer of institutional failure. One respondent from Lagos captured this as follows:

“Japa is the way to go because the politicians can no longer be trusted. They have made lots of promises for positive change, but things keep getting worse by the day and our years are running before our eyes. So Japa is our way of taking our destinies in our hands.” (Interview, Lagos, 2025).

The implications of flight over fight are paradoxical. While japa offers individuals survival, hope, and new opportunities, it simultaneously drains local institutions, weakens domestic struggles, and redefines belonging. The phenomenon, therefore, is not just about migration but about Nigeria’s contested future whether the state can provide conditions that make “fight” a viable alternative to “flight.”

Discussion

This study highlights the paradoxical positioning of African youth within contexts of constrained opportunity and expanding aspirations. By drawing on the theoretical lens of flight versus fight and exit versus voice (Hirschman, 1970), the findings show that migration is not simply a reactive escape from hardship but a strategic assertion of agency. For many young Nigerians, the Japa phenomenon embodies the rationalization of exit as a more viable pathway than voice within a governance system perceived as unresponsive or hostile. As participants repeatedly emphasized, remaining to “fight” or “speak up” often feels futile in the face of corruption, insecurity, and limited socio-economic prospects.

The narratives further suggest that exit and voice are not mutually exclusive but rather exist in tension. Migration emerges both as an individual survival strategy and as a collective indictment of state failure. The choice of flight is, therefore, simultaneously an act of disillusionment and of critique - a way of signalling the broken social contract between citizens and state. This aligns with Hirschman’s observation that widespread exit can hollow out institutions, leaving them less capable of reform, thereby reinforcing a cycle of alienation (Hirschman, 1970). In the Nigerian case, the normalization of exit demonstrates not only youth discontent but also the fragility of state legitimacy.

Moreover, the empirical findings reveal that spirituality and faith practices are woven into the migration decision-making process, complicating the dichotomy of flight and fight. Youth often interpret their choice to migrate through spiritual idioms - seeing exit not merely as a material calculation but also as divinely sanctioned. This underscores the importance of situating migration within a high-density religious landscape (Cantat, 2016; Umeh et al., 2024), where personal aspirations are legitimized through spiritual narratives.

These insights contribute to migration scholarship by challenging the crisis-focused narratives that frame African youth migration as a pathology. Instead, migration can be read as a barometer of institutional weakness, a means of navigating structural exclusion, and a testament to youth resilience. The politics of exit should, therefore, not be understood in isolation but in relation to the failure of voice and the narrowing of domestic avenues for self-realization. Unless structural reforms address the root causes of disaffection, the state risks further alienation of its citizens, with migration continuing to function both as escape and as indictment.

Conclusion

The Japa phenomenon illustrates how Nigerian youth are reconfiguring agency by choosing flight over fight in response to systemic dysfunction. Migration emerges not only as survival but as a silent critique of the state and a pursuit of dignity and aspiration. Yet, this choice also reshapes forms of engagement, as many continue to “fight from afar” through remittances, activism, and transnational solidarity. Ultimately, Japa signals a dual reality: the erosion of state legitimacy at home and the resilience of youth in reimagining futures beyond national borders. Addressing this requires more than curbing emigration; it demands systemic reforms that make staying a viable choice.

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